

**A STUDY OF ICT LITERACY AMONG THE TEACHERS WORKING IN
HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS AMONG JURISDICTION OF
NORTH MAHARASHTRA UNIVERSITY, JALGAON**

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Abstract:-

During the period of 2015-16 this survey was done. Primary data is collected from various Teachers associated with colleges and Institutes affiliated to North Maharashtra University with the help of structured questionnaire. Majority 74% mentioned that they completed some formal training on internet. When college teachers questioned whether they access email regularly then majority almost 90% claimed that they access their email on regular basis and The teachers when they asked whether they use internet for citizen e-services like railway reservation, gas booking, passport application, 7/12 abstract etc., 82.4% mentioned that they use internet for citizen E-services.

Key Words- *Affiliated, E-Services Etc.*

Introduction:-

This is the age of technology, now a day it is essential to be a smart citizen. The Government of India is changing the face of its governance by introducing new E-governance policies. The Government can achieve this goal if and only if, the citizens of India become E-literate. Of course it is the job of teacher to E-literate the peoples of local area. The present study focuses on analyzing ICT literacy among the Teachers working in higher education's institutions among Jurisdiction of North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon.

Material and Method:-

During the period of 2015-16 this survey was done. Primary data is collected from various Teachers associated with colleges and Institutes affiliated to North Maharashtra University with the help of structured questionnaire. The research practices are comprise of random sampling, data collection, data editing, data classification, tabulation and interpretation of data with the help of statistical tools.

Observation –

Table 1: Have you completed any formal training on internet? (e.g. MS-CIT)

Factor	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Have you completed any formal training on internet? (e.g. MS-CIT)	Yes	632	74
	No	222	26

Figure 1 : Have you completed any formal training on internet? (e.g. MS-CIT)

Table 2: Do you access email regularly?

Factor	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Do you access email regularly?	Yes	768	89.9
	No	86	10.1

Figure 2 : Do you access email regularly?

Table 3: Do you use internet for Social Networking? (Facebook, orkut, twitter, whats app etc.)

Factor	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Do you use internet for Social Networking? (Facebook, orkut, twitter, whats app etc.)	Yes	704	82.4
	No	150	17.6

Figure 3 : Do you access email regularly?

Table 4: Do you use internet for citizen e-services? (Like railway reservation, gas booking, passport application, 7/12 abstract etc.)

Factor	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Do you use internet for citizen e-services? (Like railway reservation, gas booking, passport application, 7/12 abstract etc.)	Yes	704	82.4
	No	150	17.6

Figure 4 : Do you access email regularly?

Result and Discussion:-

The college teachers when they asked whether they completed any formal training on internet like MS-CIT, majority 74% mentioned that they completed some formal training on internet and remaining 26% they didn't any.

When college teachers questioned whether they access email regularly then majority almost 90% claimed that they access their email on regular basis and only 10% claimed they don't.

The teachers when they asked whether they use internet for Social Networking like Facebook, orkut, twitter, whatsapp etc., majority 82.4% mentioned that they use internet for Social Networking and remaining 17.6% they didn't use internet for Social Networking

The teachers when they asked whether they use internet for citizen e-services like railway reservation, gas booking, passport application, 7/12 abstract etc., 82.4% mentioned that they use internet for citizen E-services and only 17.6% mentioned they don't use internet for citizen E-services.

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